

IMPACT OF SMARTPHONE USE ON THE MENTAL HEALTH OF TRIBAL YOUTH IN INDIA: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

This paper examines the impact of Smartphone use on the mental health of tribal youth in India, a demographic facing unique challenges due to socio-economic marginalization and limited access to mental health care. The main objective of this research is to explore how digital technologies affect the mental Health and well-being of tribal youth, focusing on both the positive and negative consequences. Digital technologies, such as mobile apps, social media and text messaging programs, offer promising mental health interventions by improving access to information, support and services. However, excessive Smartphone use has been linked to issues like anxiety, sleep disturbances, social isolation and academic difficulties. The study utilizes secondary data from various peer-reviewed articles, reports and publications gathered from databases like Google Scholar, ResearchGate and government sources. This review synthesizes findings from empirical studies, government initiatives and global research to provide insights into the complex relationship between Smartphone use and mental health. It is revealed from the review of literature that the dual impact of mobile phone use on tribal youth's mental health, highlighting both benefits for access to care and risks like addiction, anxiety and cultural disconnection.

Keywords: *Mental Health, Technological Impact, Tribal Youth, Digital behaviour, Cultural identity, India*

Introduction

The increasing accessibility of smartphones in India's rural and tribal areas has brought both advantages and challenges for young people. While mobile technology offers valuable tools for learning, connection, and information access, it also raises serious concerns regarding its influence on mental health, behaviour and cultural continuity among tribal youth. India's
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tribal population, constituting around 8.6% of the national total, often resides in regions with minimal mental health infrastructure but is rapidly integrating into the digital ecosystem (Census of India, 2011). According to the *ASER 2024* report, 82.2% of rural adolescents aged 14–16 use smartphones, yet only 57% use them for educational purposes, while 76% primarily engage in social media (The Print, 2024). This shift in usage patterns is linked to rising mental health concerns. The *Economic Survey of India* attributes a national increase in psychological issues to excessive internet and social media use (Economic Times, 2023). Though specific data on tribal youth is limited, the *National Mental Health Survey* (2015–16) reports that 10.6% of Indian adults suffer from mental disorders, with treatment gaps exceeding 70% (NIMHANS, 2016). However, a sociological investigation among the Rabha tribe in West Bengal found that increased smartphone dependency among youth is contributing to a decline in real-world social engagement and shifts in communication habits (Bordoloi & Dutta, 2023).

In recent years, India has witnessed a remarkable surge in Smartphone penetration, extending even into its most remote tribal regions. According to the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI), “mobile subscriptions in rural India reached over 500 million by the end of 2023, a significant portion of which includes tribal populations.” This digital expansion has enabled greater access to information, education and connectivity, fundamentally transforming the socio-cultural fabric of tribal communities. However, as the digital divide narrows, a new set of challenges emerges; particularly concerning the mental health of tribal youth, a demographic already vulnerable due to socio-economic marginalization, limited healthcare access, and cultural stigmas surrounding mental illness. The impact of Smart phone use on mental health is increasingly drawing attention from policymakers and public health experts. A major governmental initiative, the SMART Mental Health Project, implemented by The George Institute for Global Health in collaboration with India’s National Mental Health Programme, demonstrated “the potential of digital tools to address mental health challenges in rural and tribal areas. In Andhra Pradesh alone, the project trained community health workers to screen and refer individuals for depression and anxiety using mobile apps. The result was a staggering 1,500-fold increase in mental health service uptake among tribal populations, many of whom had never received any form of psychological care before (The George Institute).” While such interventions are promising, the broader and often unsupervised use of Smartphones among tribal youth has also been associated with emerging risks. A government survey in Himachal Pradesh conducted in 2023 revealed that nearly

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19.6% of youths aged 10–24 showed signs of Smartphone addiction, while 15.5% experienced moderate to severe anxiety symptoms. This data aligns with findings from the Economic Survey 2023-24, which explicitly pointed to the overuse of social media and digital devices as a growing public health concern in India, especially among children and adolescents (Ministry of Finance, 2023).

Recent studies have shown that Indigenous communities, especially younger individuals, are increasingly bridging the digital divide due to advancements in mobile technology. Compared to older generations, Indigenous youth are more likely to integrate digital tools into their everyday lives. Supporting this trend a national survey in the United States found that 78 per cent of 675 American Indian and Alaska Native (AI/AN) teenagers and young adults regularly use smartphones (Rushing, Stephens, & Dog, 2018). According to Carlson et al. (2015) propose that “Indigenous individuals are more open to informal help-seeking approaches, such as the use of digital media, which can help them overcome barriers that hinder them from accessing formal mental health services. Mobile technology holds significant potential in delivering mental health programs, services, and interventions to Indigenous people who face challenges with their mental health.” Furthermore, a study in 2021 supported by the National Commission for Protection of Child Rights (NCPCR) highlighted that nearly 37% of children across India reported diminished concentration and increased irritability due to prolonged smartphone usage (NCPCR, 2021). These trends are even more concerning in tribal regions, where digital literacy is low and the support systems for mental health are often absent. As tribal youth engage more with digital content, ranging from social media to gaming; they are increasingly exposed to cyberbullying, sleep disturbances and social isolation, all of which are linked to poor mental health outcomes. In this context, the dual role of Smartphones, as both enablers of mental healthcare and potential sources of psychological distress, creates a complex scenario that demands careful examination. For tribal youth, who often lack the institutional safeguards and familial awareness that mitigate such impacts in urban settings, the psychological cost of unchecked digital exposure may be far more severe. Therefore, this research paper aims to critically evaluate the nuanced relationship between mobile phone use and mental health among the tribal youth, drawing on empirical data, government-backed initiatives and field-based assessments.

Objectives of the study

The following are the objectives of the study;

1. To investigate the impact of Smartphone use on the mental health and well-being of tribal youth.
2. To review the relationship between Smartphone usage and social behaviour among Tribal youth.
3. To analyse the cultural implications of Smartphone use on the identity of tribal youth.

Methodology

This study utilizes a qualitative systematic literature review approach to investigate the impact of smartphone usage on the mental health of tribal youth in India. The review article is based exclusively on secondary data derived from peer-reviewed journal articles, government reports, and institutional publications. A comprehensive and structured literature search was conducted from 2014 to 2024 across multiple databases, including Google Scholar, ResearchGate, PubMed, ScienceDirect, and official platforms of the Ministry of Tribal Affairs and the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR). The search strategy utilized Boolean operators and key terms such as “Smartphone use” AND “mental health” AND (“tribal youth” OR “Indigenous youth”) AND (“India” OR “global Indigenous populations”). Additional terms included “smartphone addiction,” “digital mental health,” “social behaviour,” and “cultural identity.” Inclusion criteria comprised English-language studies published between 2014 to 2024 that focused on tribal or Indigenous youth aged 10–24, addressed mental health outcomes (e.g., anxiety, depression, behavioural changes), and employed qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods. Exclusion criteria included studies not centered on mental health or tribal populations and non-scholarly sources. After an initial screening of titles and abstracts, full-text reviews were conducted, resulting in a final set of studies that met all eligibility requirements. Key data were extracted and analysed to identify patterns, challenges and research gaps related to Smartphone use and mental health.

Literature review

Hicks et al. (2024) carried out a systematic review to explore the development and implementation of electronic mental health interventions designed for Indigenous youth facing mental health challenges. This review was prompted by a noticeable rise in both the number of relevant studies and the urgent demand for digital support during periods of increased isolation, such as during pandemics. The researchers examined 48 peer-reviewed and grey literature sources, identifying smoking cessation and suicide prevention as the most

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frequently addressed issues. The study highlighted text messaging and smartphone applications as the dominant modes of intervention delivery. The reviewed studies featured qualitative, quantitative and mixed-methods outcomes, along with detailed accounts of intervention development and research protocols, reflecting a rapidly expanding area of research. Findings showed a focus on smoking cessation and suicide, with text messaging and apps as common tools. Cultural relevance, community involvement and resource limitations emerged as key facilitators and barriers to intervention success.

Li and Brar's (2022) in their study carefully reviewed 27 empirical papers from four different nations in order to evaluate the effects of digital technology on the mental health and wellbeing of Indigenous people. It examined how Indigenous communities interact with digital media and use e-mental health (eMH) resources. The review analysed research objectives, measurement tools and themes related to eMH adoption. Findings indicated that digital technologies can effectively support Indigenous mental health, especially when designed using decolonizing, culturally appropriate approaches. The study offers practical insights for researchers, health professionals and educators developing digital mental health interventions.

Chattopadhyay and Seemita Mohanty (2022) conducted a qualitative study to investigate how digital media influences the social and cultural lives of Lodha tribal youth in Odisha's Mayurbhanj district. The study focused on the connection between new media usage and experiences of cultural exclusion. Data were gathered using face-to-face interviews, focus group discussions and observational methods across five Lodha-majority villages, employing stratified random sampling. Findings revealed that increased digital media access led to a growing disconnect from traditional customs, with youth adopting urbanized lifestyles. The study highlighted how digital exposure is reshaping cultural identity, distancing the younger generation from the beliefs and practices of their elders and traditional community life.

Das and Debbarma (2021) in their paper explored smartphone use among tribal youth in Tripura, focusing on its impact on academic and personal life. Surveying 852 students, the study found excessive use leading to poor academic performance, reduced concentration, and limited social interaction. Despite socio-economic barriers, tribal youth showed usage patterns similar to urban peers. The study highlights the need for digital literacy and balanced smartphone use to reduce negative effects.

Toombs et al. (2020) in their study conducted a systematic review of electronic health interventions for mental health concerns among Indigenous populations by analysing peer-

reviewed and grey literature. The reviewed studies employed various digital platforms for interventions targeting substance use, suicide prevention, parenting and behaviour change. Most studies presented qualitative findings, while fewer reported quantitative outcomes. The review identified both barriers and facilitators to implementation, showing early promise in Indigenous engagement. However, further research is needed to validate these findings and guide future intervention development.

Abi-Jaoude et al. (2020) in their paper conducted a study on the relationship between smartphone and social media use and mental health issues among adolescents, focusing on distress, suicidality, academic performance and socioemotional functioning. It finds that excessive use leads to negative outcomes, particularly among girls, including sleep deprivation, cognitive impairments and social comparison. The research highlights the need for public awareness, clinician-family collaboration and policy initiatives to mitigate these impacts. Interventions should focus on fostering resilience and healthy media use in adolescents.

Christie et al. (2019) developed “*Quest – Te Whitianga*,” a gamified mobile app offering cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) to Māori and Pasifika youth in New Zealand. Designed through a co-creation process with clinicians, youth and game designers, the app uses engaging modules set in a virtual island journey, incorporating mindfulness, gratitude journaling, and communication skills. While trial results are pending, the app shows promise as an accessible, engaging mental health tool for underserved youth.

Sohn et al. (2019) carried out a systematic review and meta-analysis to assess how widespread problematic smartphone use (PSU) is among children and young people (CYP) and to explore its connection to adverse mental health outcomes. The methods included searching eight databases for relevant studies from 2011 to 2017, with 41 studies included. The major findings revealed that 23.3% of CYP experienced PSU, which was linked to increased depression, anxiety, stress and poorer sleep quality. The study concluded that PSU is a public health concern requiring further research and policy guidance.

Tighe et al. (2017) in their paper stated that the efficacy of the *ibobbly* mobile app, which targets impulsivity, depression, psychological distress, and suicide ideation in Indigenous teenagers in outback Australia. The Kimberley region's participants, who were between the ages of 18 and 35, were randomly assigned to either receive the app or be placed on a waiting. The primary outcome was suicidal ideation (measured by DSI-SS), with secondary outcomes including depression and distress scales. Results showed significant reductions in

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depression and distress in the app group, though no significant changes in suicidal ideation or impulsivity. The study concluded that self-help apps can effectively reduce distress and depression in remote communities.

Nishad and Rana (2016) in their study explore to the role of cell phones in daily life, particularly focusing on their importance for communication, social interaction, and emergency situations. The research methods likely involve examining how individuals use cell phones for various activities, including staying connected with family, engaging in online activities and seeking help during emergencies. Major findings highlight the convenience, flexibility and social benefits cell phones offer, emphasizing their essential role in modern communication and their ability to provide security and emergency assistance.

Rice et al. (2016) observed that how Indigenous Australian youth use social media and digital technologies, focusing on both positive and negative impacts. Online literature searches were conducted in several databases, and 22 papers were included in the review. Thematic analysis identified key themes, including identity, community connections and health promotion. Positive uses included enhancing cultural identity and improving health outcomes, while negative aspects like cyberbullying and cyber racism were also noted. The study suggests further research to minimize misuse and enhance the positive potential of social media in health interventions.

Bartgis and Albright (2016) in their study evaluate the effectiveness of an online avatar-based gatekeeper training program for American Indian and Alaska Native (AI/AN) youth and educators. Using realistic, emotionally responsive avatars, the training helped participants practice recognizing and responding to signs of psychological distress. Data from 86 matched participants showed significant improvements in preparedness, behavioural intent and self-efficacy to assist distressed individuals, sustained at a 3-month follow-up. The findings suggest that online simulations are a promising tool for culturally relevant suicide prevention and mental health support in AI/AN communities, addressing existing barriers to traditional gatekeeper training in these populations.

Demirci et al. (2015) examine how university students' levels of smartphone use relate to their anxiety, sadness and sleep quality. Based on their use of smartphones, 319 students were divided into three groups. The Smartphone Addiction Scale, Beck Depression Inventory, Beck Anxiety Inventory and Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index were used in the procedures. The findings revealed that high smartphone use was linked to higher depression, anxiety and sleep

disturbances, with females showing significantly higher addiction scores than males, highlighting the impact of smartphone overuse on mental health.

Brusse et al. (2014) examined Australian and international data on the use of social media and smartphone applications for health promotion, with an emphasis on Indigenous Australians' use of media for otitis media, sexual health and quitting smoking. The study concluded that Indigenous-focused treatments had no discernible advantages and were only moderately successful. These technologies are widely used, although their effect and acceptance are modest. In order to comprehend user involvement and create evidence-based, culturally relevant digital health solutions, the study urges more research.

Findings and Discussion

The growing integration of Smartphones and digital technologies into the daily lives of tribal and Indigenous youth has generated widespread academic interest, particularly regarding its influence on mental health and well-being. A critical synthesis of the existing literature reveals a complex relationship, where digital technologies present both opportunities for support and engagement, as well as risks and barriers, especially in marginalized and geographically isolated communities. This discussion draws upon diverse empirical studies and systematic reviews to assess both the positive and negative implications of Smartphone use and related digital technologies for Indigenous youth, with particular relevance to tribal populations in India. The potential benefits of digital and mobile technologies in improving mental health among Indigenous youth are well documented. Hicks et al. (2024) and Li & Brar (2022) highlight that “digital mental health (eMH) interventions—such as mobile apps, text-based services, and online platforms; offer culturally appropriate, accessible support mechanisms in settings where formal mental health services are scarce. These interventions frequently address issues such as depression, anxiety, suicide prevention and substance use. Importantly, the success of these programs is closely tied to the inclusion of cultural relevance and community engagement.” Tools like the *ibobbly* app, reviewed in Tighe et al. (2017), demonstrate the potential of mobile-based, self-help mental health interventions in reducing psychological distress and depressive symptoms, particularly when designed with Indigenous perspectives in mind.

Moreover, digital technologies have shown to foster positive psychosocial outcomes by enhancing cultural identity, community belonging, and resilience. Studies such as those by Rice et al. (2016) and Carlson et al. (2015), “emphasize how social media platforms are used by Indigenous youth not only for communication but also as a space to affirm identity, *Copyright@2025 Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science & English Language*

connect with peers, and engage in cultural expression. Such usage can contribute to improved mental health and reduced isolation by reinforcing familial and community ties; factors widely recognized as protective against mental health challenges.”

However, the literature also reveals considerable risks and limitations associated with digital media use among Indigenous and tribal youth. A major concern is “the emergence of negative behaviors such as cyberbullying, cyber racism, and the exchange of explicit content, particularly in unregulated online spaces (Rice et al., 2016).” These activities are linked to heightened stress, anxiety, and social withdrawal. Furthermore, Sohn et al. (2019) and Demirci et al. (2015), “provide meta-analytic and empirical evidence demonstrating a strong correlation between problematic smartphone use (PSU) and adverse mental health outcomes, including sleep disturbances, depression, and cognitive impairments”. These findings are especially significant given that tribal youth in India; despite socio-economic disparities, demonstrate mobile phone usage patterns comparable to their urban peers (Das & Debbarma, 2021). Another recurring theme in the literature is the cultural and generational disconnection that may arise from excessive mobile and digital media use. The qualitative study by Chattopadhyay & Mohanty (2022) highlights that increased digital engagement among Lodha tribal youth in Odisha has led to a noticeable departure from traditional customs and lifestyles. This digital cultural shift may contribute to identity confusion and intergenerational tensions, particularly in communities where oral traditions and elder knowledge transmission are core to social cohesion and psychological stability. From a structural standpoint, several studies underscore the persistent digital divide faced by Indigenous and tribal populations. Despite the rising adoption of Smartphones, particularly among youth, infrastructural limitations such as poor internet access, low digital literacy, and a lack of culturally tailored digital resources continue to restrict the efficacy of interventions (Toombs et al., 2020; Hicks et al., 2024). This is particularly true in remote tribal areas of India, where educational and economic barriers intersect with technological limitations, thereby reducing the scalability and reach of digital mental health solutions.

Despite these limitations, several innovations provide insights for future research and intervention strategies. The gamified mental health app Quest – Te Whitianga, developed by Christie et al. (2019) for Māori and Pasifika youth, demonstrates the promise of co-designed digital tools in engaging underserved populations through culturally relevant narratives and interactive modules. Similarly, Bartgis & Albright (2016) illustrate how online simulations

using avatars can provide effective mental health training and gatekeeping skills in American Indian and Alaska Native communities, addressing gaps left by conventional interventions. In synthesizing these findings, it becomes evident that while digital technologies offer transformative potential in supporting the mental health of Indigenous and tribal youth, their effectiveness is highly dependent on several contextual factors. Foremost among these is cultural congruence, interventions that fail to embed Indigenous worldviews, languages, and values often face poor uptake and limited impact. Community involvement throughout the design and implementation process is also critical, ensuring that the tools developed are not only technologically accessible but socially and culturally resonant. For tribal youth in India, these lessons carry urgent relevance. As Smartphone penetration continues to rise, especially among the younger generation, there is both a challenge and an opportunity. The challenge lies in mitigating the psychological risks associated with overuse, isolation and cultural disconnection. The opportunity, however, is in leveraging mobile platforms to deliver scalable, localized, and culturally embedded mental health interventions; potentially overcoming the longstanding barriers posed by geographic remoteness and healthcare inaccessibility. In conclusion, the existing body of literature offers a nuanced understanding of how Smartphone use and digital technologies impact the mental health of Indigenous and tribal youth. While the benefits are clear, ranging from increased access to care and cultural affirmation to community-building and the risks cannot be ignored. A critical path forward involves the development of community-led, culturally safe digital interventions that prioritize both technological innovation and Indigenous knowledge systems. For Indian tribal youth, such an approach could significantly contribute to closing the mental health equity gap.

Conclusion

This review paper examines the impact of smartphone and digital technology use on the mental health of tribal youth, with a particular focus on the Indian context. The literature reveals that culturally tailored and community-driven digital interventions; such as mobile apps, messaging platforms and social media, can effectively address mental health challenges including depression, distress and social isolation, especially in remote or underserved areas. These technologies offer significant potential when they are co-designed with Indigenous communities, aligned with local values, and supported by adequate infrastructure. However, concerns persist regarding excessive Smartphone use, which has been linked to anxiety, sleep disturbances and reduced academic and social functioning. Additionally, digital engagement

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may contribute to cultural disconnection if not balanced with traditional practices. Key barriers such as poor infrastructure, lack of culturally relevant content and limited digital literacy must be addressed. For Indian tribal youth, there is a pressing need for region-specific, gender-sensitive and longitudinal research that integrates traditional knowledge with modern digital approaches. When appropriately developed and implemented, digital technologies can serve as powerful tools for promoting mental health and cultural resilience, helping to reduce persistent health disparities in tribal populations. Therefore, a comprehensive literature evaluation is crucial for the creation of future treatments, instructional methods, and additional research. The evidence and possibility of using a variety of digital technologies to enhance the mental health of Indigenous people in various age groups and nations will be critically examined in this study. This study is very much necessary since there aren't many previous literature studies that focus on this particular topic.

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